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WIND IN MY BACKYARD

WIMBY

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SHORT ABSTRACT FOR DISSEMINATION PURPOSES

Abstract

D1.3 describes the first version of the dataset created in task 1.2: Land & Sea Use And Change. The deliverable is the outcome of various data analyses, starting from raw data compilation of Copernicus Sentinel-2 satellite images from 2015 – 2023, the development of region-dependent algorithms for change detection, and the statistical analyses of the change data. The provision of this data is paramount for many tasks in WP3 and also tasks in other work-packages. The change dataset has a spatial resolution of 10m x 10m and is a binary raster dataset visualizing changes beneath and around wind turbine locations, which were built between 2015 and 2023. The statistical analysis consists of vector data and is based on the change raster, land-cover data, the biogeographical region and terrain data. The statistical calculations are made on a per wind turbine basis, but also for wind parks comprising a set of wind turbines. Currently data analysis is ongoing work and consists of a set of EU countries (Austria, Denmark, Italy, Norway and Portugal) and will be extended further during the next months.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. INTRODUCTION	10
2. MATERIAL AND METHODS	12
2.1 Input Data Overview	12
2.1.1 Satellite data	12
2.1.2 Wind turbine data.....	12
2.1.3 Land Use and Land Cover data	13
2.1.4 Terrain Data.....	13
2.1.5 Environmental Data.....	13
2.1.6 Territorial units	14
2.2 Sentinel-2 Processing.....	14
2.2.1 Sentinel-2 Preprocessing.....	15
2.2.1 Change Detection	16
2.3 Statistical Analysis.....	19
2.3.1 Single turbine analysis.....	20
2.3.2 Cluster analysis.....	20
3. DATA AND RESULTS	22
3.1 Sentinel-2 Data	22
3.1.1 Sentinel-2 Preprocessing.....	22
3.1.2 Change Detection	24
3.1 Statistical Analysis.....	26
3.1.1 Single turbine analysis.....	26
3.1.2 Cluster analysis.....	27
4. OUTLOOK.....	29
5. CONCLUSIONS.....	30
REFERENCES	31
ANNEX.....	35

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ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Description
WP	Work Package
EU	European Union
USGS	United States Geological Survey
NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
ESA	European Space Agency
OSM	OpenStreetMap
EEA	European Economic Area
EPSG	European Petroleum Service Group – Geodetic Parameter Dataset
CORINE	Coordination of Information on the Environment
DEM	Digital Elevation Models
NUTS	Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics
JP2, JPEG2000	Join Photographic Experts Group
GML	Generalized Markup Language
IQ	Isoperimetric Quotient
SI	Shape Index
FD	Fractal Dimension
DBSCAN	Density based spatial clustering of applications with noise

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1. Biogeographical Regions in Europe (by EEA)..... 14

Figure 2. Flowchart showing the Data preparation..... 15

Figure 3. Flowchart showing the Sentinel-2 data download and processing17

Figure 4. Flow Chart of the change detection analysis 18

Figure 5. Concave (blue) and convex (red) hull example..... 21

Figure 6. Newly installed wind turbine locations in Italy from 2015 to 2023 .. 22

Figure 7. Sentinel-2 detail of a wind park in an agricultural area before construction..... 23

Figure 8. Sentinel-2 detail of a wind park in an agricultural area after construction..... 23

Figure 9. Change map of a wind park in an agricultural area, grey indicating zero change, red/violet positive values, green / blue negative values. 25

Figure 10. Binary Change Map of the agricultural example 25

Figure 11. Channel 2 - change sum: vertical versus horizontal, red depicting all turbines in the analysis, blue showing the ones built between 2015 and 2023..... 26

Figure 12. Single Turbine Analysis using a 150m buffer..... 26

Figure 13. Cluster Analysis of newly built (2015-2023) turbines east of Vienna 27

Figure 14. Convex Hull example around a single wind park area 28

Figure 15. Sentinel-2 tiles with at least one wind turbine in Italy 35

Figure 16. Sentinel-2 detail of a wind park in a mountainous region before construction..... 36

Figure 17. Sentinel-2 detail of a wind park in a mountainous region after construction..... 36

Figure 18. Change map of a wind park in a forested mountain region, grey indicating zero change, red/violet positive values, green / blue negative values. 37

Figure 19. Binary change map of the mountainous area 37

Figure 20. Change Map Offshore Turbines, grey indicating no change..... 38

Figure 21. Binary Change Map Offshore Turbines..... 38

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report provides a description of the datasets generated in Task 1.2: Land & Sea Use and Change. The task started from month 1 and will be finished until month 18. The current status of the data compilation consists of a set of EU countries (Austria, Denmark, Italy, Norway and Portugal) and will be extended further during the next months until month 18.

The deliverable encompasses the results obtained through a series of data analyses. These analyses involve compiling raw data derived from Copernicus Sentinel-2 satellite photos spanning the period from 2015 to 2023. Additionally, the creation of algorithms specific to different regions (EU countries & sub-regions) for the purpose of detecting changes, as well as the subsequent statistical analysis of the change data, are integral components of this process. The change dataset possesses the same spatial resolution as the input data from Sentinel-2, 10m x 10m, and represents a binary raster dataset that visually represents the alterations occurring beneath and in the vicinity of wind turbine sites, which were constructed between the years 2015 and 2023. The statistical analysis encompasses vector data and examines the change raster, land-cover data, the biogeographical area, and terrain data. The statistical computations are performed using single wind turbines, as well as for wind parks consisting of many wind turbines.

The availability of this data is of utmost importance for many activities in WP3 as well as those in other work-packages. The resulting dataset will be further used by various tasks, including T1.4, T1.5, and also tasks in WPs 4 and 5. First results show that the extent and the pattern of the changes differ significantly by country and regions, by previous land use and land cover pattern, and they are of course also influenced by the terrain.

1. INTRODUCTION

It is commonly acknowledged that satisfying energy demands while reducing harmful climate change is a concern. However, there is another challenge that demands consideration as well: the effects of expanding energy demand on land usage. Energy development's expanding land use footprint, sometimes known as "energy sprawl," is predicted to have a major negative impact on biodiversity and ecosystem services through habitat loss and fragmentation (Trainor et al., 2016). In general, there are two major types of land use changes by wind power plants: a) direct impacts, and b) total area (Denholm et al., 2009). The first identifies the disturbed land due to the development of the plant (foundation) itself. The latter depicts further changes involved in the deployment of wind turbines, for example (permanent) service roads, temporary roads or storage areas.

A wind power plant's development causes a range of disturbances, both short-term and long-term (Arnett et al., 2007). Wind turbine pads, access roads, substations, service buildings, and other equipment that physically occupy land or produce impermeable surfaces are examples of these disruptions. Development in forested areas, where more land must be removed around each turbine, is linked to extra direct impacts. Although the land cleared around a turbine pad does not produce impermeable surfaces, the quality of the ecosystem may be significantly degraded as a result of this alteration. Construction of the plant has transitory effects in addition to permanent ones that last the facility's lifetime. These effects are related to lay-down, storage, and temporary construction access roads. Following the completion of plant building, these locations will ultimately revert to their pre-construction form.

In order to examine the impact of wind power infrastructure on land and sea, it is necessary to conduct an analysis with a high level of spatial resolution in order to accurately depict the changes resulting from the installations. At the same time it is necessary to differentiate between onshore and offshore development patterns (Enevoldsen & Jacobson, 2021). Present and proposed wind parks in Europe are identified by analysing actual location data and these locations are analysed if and to which extent they act as a driver to cause land- and sea use changes. The research takes into account additional factors such as topography, altitude landscape characteristics, and also infrastructure (i.e. roads). The produced output is further consolidated and made accessible for further case studies and mapping

assignments. The provided data is also used in further analysis of disturbances regarding terrestrial fauna, but also aquatic life.

This report provides a description of methods for the analysis of land use associated with the deployment of wind power plants. Furthermore, the data output is described using examples.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Input Data Overview

2.1.1 Satellite data

Satellite data include both satellite images and earth observation data, which collectively offer valuable insights into the characteristics of the planet's surface and its atmospheric conditions. High-resolution photographs of the Earth provide data for several dynamic aspects of our planet, including alterations in land cover, cloud cover, ocean levels, ice cover, and atmospheric composition. The majority of satellites employed for data collection are launched and operated by governmental entities, including the United States Geological Survey (USGS), the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), and the European Space Agency (ESA). Besides those governmental entities, there are also private enterprises that work within this particular industry.

While some commercial satellites, including SkySat, collect imagery at very high resolutions of down to 0.5m x 0.5m but only date back to 2020, the long running Landsat only offers only a resolution of 30m x 30m, which is unsuitable for our analysis. Hence, it was decided to use data of the Copernicus Sentinel-2 project (Drusch et al., 2012) which offers a spatial resolution of 10m x 10m and a history back to 2015, and also available for free. The resolution is sufficient to distinguish wind turbines from other land-cover, such as agricultural fields or forests.

2.1.2 Wind turbine data

OpenStreetMap (OSM) functions as a helpful platform for the aggregation and presentation of data (OpenStreetMap contributors, 2023), including wind turbines, and therefore provides a mostly complete and easily available dataset. OSM not only provides the location of wind turbines, but sometimes also hub-height, capacity and other turbine specifics. The provided data not only facilitates the visualisation of the worldwide distribution of wind energy infrastructure, but also acts as a valuable resource for academics. The up-to-date character of OSM is facilitated by its collaborative framework, which enables the inclusion of developing

information about wind energy projects, e.g., the approximate construction date of a wind turbine.

2.1.3 Land Use and Land Cover data

The EEA has established the CORINE Land Cover database (European Environment Agency, 2019), which serves as a comprehensive resource for land-use and land-cover information. The dataset offers insights into the land cover patterns observed in the EU, but also Norway, Switzerland and Turkey. It encompasses a wide range of distinct categories, including agricultural land and forests. The use of CORINE Land Cover data has significant importance in the WIMBY project as we can specifically analyse alterations in land utilization patterns at wind turbine locations and the vicinity of turbines.

2.1.4 Terrain Data

Terrain data, specifically Digital Elevation Models (DEMs), have significant importance in the field of geospatial analysis and environmental research. DEMs offer a comprehensive depiction of the earth's topographic height, effectively capturing the diverse range of terrain fluctuations. The measurement of slope, which is a crucial element in the analysis of topography, is used to determine the degree of steepness of the ground surface. Ruggedness, an essential measure obtained from a DEM, serves to quantify the degree of variation in elevation within a given geographical region, hence providing valuable insights on the topographic intricacies of the area. The combination of several terrain data factors is used in the analyses for statistical purposes to provide more detailed information for similar landscape types. As a source for the DEM, we facilitate the freely available Copernicus GLO-30 and GLO-90 datasets (European Space Agency & Airbus, 2022).

2.1.5 Environmental Data

The EEA classified bioregions as distinct geographic areas that exhibit comparable ecological traits (see Figure 1). This classification enables a comprehension of ecosystem distribution and functioning throughout Europe. The bioregions play a crucial role in the WIMBY project, as statistical

data for land-use change will be calculated in alignment with these regions. In addition, we utilize environmental zones from the EEA, which encompass a range of climatic, topographic, and human activity variables (Metzger, 2018).

Figure 1. Biogeographical Regions in Europe (by EEA)

2.1.6 Territorial units

The Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics (NUTS) is a hierarchical framework employed to partition European nations into regions provided by Eurostat, serving statistical and administrative objectives. The NUTS dataset (EuroStat, 2020) plays a vital role in the standardized statistical aggregation of the results within this task.

2.2 Sentinel-2 Processing

2.2.1 Sentinel-2 Preprocessing

A flow chart visualizing the data preparation and preprocessing is shown in Figure 2. In the initial stage of the study of Land Use Change, data on wind turbines is collected for each country in the European Union. Using the value "wind" and the values "plant:source" and "generator:source" these data sets are queried from the OSM data using either the *QuickOSM* toolbox included in the QGIS software, or by a python script. It is necessary to identify the Sentinel-2 coverage and tile names for the region / country of interest, in order to have the necessary information for later processing. After selecting one wind turbine location for each tile, the location is then recorded as a point shapefile in the Web Mercator projection *EPSG:3857*. The tile name, e.g., *32TNK*, is something that can be obtained by intersecting this point shapefile with the Sentinel-2 tiling grid. The tile name is one of the parameters that may be used to query and download scenes from the Google Sentintel-2 Cloud (Google Earth Engine, 2023).

Figure 2. Flowchart showing the Data preparation

Figure 3 visualizes the processing of the tiles prepared in the previous step. Included in the list of additional criteria for the Sentinel-2 tiles is a predetermined value for the maximum cloud coverage, i.e., 5%, as well as a specified time period for the years 2015 and 2023. The time frame is modified in accordance with the climatic and vegetation zones of the region / country which are analysed, with the intention of avoiding snow covering as well as periods of dense vegetation, as the change detection between two different years is likely to produce invalid values or is simply very hard to interpret. After the files have been downloaded, a check is performed to determine whether or not the pixel data for the wind turbine is legitimate and relevant. This includes a point where the raster outline and the wind turbine location intersect, applying a buffer of one hundred meters. In order to process the raster outline, a byte conversion is performed on one band of the dataset, in our case band 3 – green is used. This results in values of "1" indicating pixels that have valid data and "0" indicating pixels that do not contain any data values. After this, the polygonization of valid pixels, also known as the "raster outline," is performed. If the wind turbine is located outside the raster outline the raster file is discarded and a fresh scene is fetched from the Google Cloud and the process is repeated. In case the wind turbine is situated within the raster outline, the analysis proceeds with the intersection with the provided cloud mask from the Sentinel-2 dataset. The cloud mask is usually provided as either a JP2, jpeg2000 image standard, or GML (geography markup language) file format, which is converted to the shapefile format in order to perform the intersection. In the event that the wind turbine is under cloud cover, a fresh scene is downloaded. Following the discovery of valid scenes for the years 2015 and 2023, a procedure known as "Sen2Cor" (Main-Knorn et al., 2017) is performed. Sen2Cor is a collection of tools developed by the ESA for the purpose of correcting atmospheric and terrain conditions. For our purposes the atmospheric adjustment correction is applied to the downloaded datasets.

2.2.1 Change Detection

The process of the change detection is visualized in Figure 3. Once the necessary steps of download and preprocessing are finished, a change detection raster map is constructed using true colour images that have been acquired from the Sen2Cor output. This raster map is created using the open source toolbox Orfeo (Grizonnet et al., 2017). In order to obtain

information on the amount of land that wind power facilities use, this map is utilised. First, raster values will be recovered for the OSM wind power plant point data, which also include the four consecutive pixels, north and south, east and west. In order to compute the horizontal and vertical sums, which

Figure 3. Flowchart showing the Sentinel-2 data download and processing

give extra information on whether or not the pixel value has changed, these 4 neighbouring pixels are included in the calculation. In most cases, negative pixel values imply a change, and this information is used to filter out wind turbines that were constructed between the years 2015 and 2023. For actual wind turbine points, square meter and hectare values of change are extracted by employing a change detection map filtering the negative change values. By applying the filter on positive change values, the algorithm is also capable of detecting the removal of wind turbines, for example to detect changes of repowering measures, where generally many smaller wind turbines are replaced with fewer but larger designs.

Figure 4. Flow Chart of the change detection analysis

2.3 Statistical Analysis

The methodology employs statistical analysis to quantify and validate the observed changes. For the purpose of descriptive statistics, time series analysis is utilised to evaluate the statistical significance and geographical arrangement of identified changes.

The values calculated include: total change (m²) and change percentage (%), but also values describing the shape of the change patterns (aggregate of consecutive pixel which changed).

Shape analysis is fundamental for identifying and describing patterns in the landscape. Currently, no single satisfactory method for shape analysis in GIS has been developed. But numerous indices to describe shapes exist to allow a comparison:

a) Compactness / Isoperimetric Quotient (IQ)

A measure to quantify the degree to which a shape is compact (Polsby & Popper, 1991), where a circle, IQ = 1, represents the most compact planar shape and very complex polygons will give values of below 0.2. Parameter a in the equation stands for the area, p for the perimeter:

$$IQ = 4\pi \frac{a}{p^2}$$

b) Shape Index (SI)

The shape index (McGarigal, 1995) is similar to the compactness measure presented above, but increases from circular or square shapes which are represented by a value of 1 and has no upper bound as shapes become more irregular:

$$SI = \frac{p}{2\sqrt{\pi a}}$$

c) Fractal Dimension (FD)

Commonly used to measure (Rutledge, 2003) the degree of shape complexity. Varies from 1, simple shapes such as circles and squares, to 2, which indicates complex shapes:

$$FD = \frac{2 \ln p}{\ln a}$$

2.3.1 Single turbine analysis

For the single turbine change analysis a predefined buffer around one wind turbine is created and the indices above are calculated. Currently this work is ongoing and various buffer sizes are subject to be tested.

2.3.2 Cluster analysis

Apart from the single turbine analysis we quantify land-use changes for whole wind park developed, to grasp the effects on the environment from whole set of turbines erected.

To accomplish this the following tasks are performed:

1. Cluster analysis using the DBSCAN algorithm (Schubert et al., 2017)
The algorithm is run with a minimum cluster size of 2 (meaning one wind park consists of at least two turbines) and a maximum distance between clustered points of 1500 meters.
2. A nearest neighbour analysis is performed to get the average distance between points.
3. Based on the average distance buffers, concave hulls and convex hulls are used to create the park areas.
A convex hull is the minimal convex polygon that encompasses a set of points in a two-dimensional plane. The term refers to the common area shared by all convex sets that include the specified points. On the other hand, a concave hull is a shape that encloses a set of points but can have indentations or concavities. It is designed to better represent the non-convex geometry of certain point sets. An example of a convex and concave hull is presented in Figure 5.
4. Within these areas the above indices are calculated.

Figure 5. Concave (blue) and convex (red) hull example

3. DATA AND RESULTS

3.1 Sentinel-2 Data

3.1.1 Sentinel-2 Preprocessing

Figure 6 shows turbines in Italy erected between 2015 and 2023 as an example for an OSM Turbine download. This dataset is then used to download the corresponding tiles in Italy for further processing for the change detection.

Figure 6. Newly installed wind turbine locations in Italy from 2015 to 2023

Detailed examples of a true colour images from Sentinel-2 for a wind park within an agricultural area can be viewed in Figure 7 and Figure 8. Figure 7 shows the satellite image before the construction of wind turbines, but with

the know locations from OSM marked with yellow dots. The Figure 8 shows the same situation after the built-up of the turbines.

Figure 7. Sentinel-2 detail of a wind park in an agricultural area before construction

Figure 8. Sentinel-2 detail of a wind park in an agricultural area after construction

3.1.2 Change Detection

Based on the *before construction* and *after construction* tiles the change calculation is performed and exemplary results are visualized in Figure 9. Figure 9 shows the change image for the agricultural area presented above. The colours indicate changes with negative (blue-green) to positive values (red-purple) in varying intensity, while grey represents areas without changes. Additionally, the image also shows changes in agriculture, e.g. varying crops / crop rotations, and also natural changes can be observed, e.g. due to varying weather in the comparison years.

As described in the methodology further assessment to filter and extract the anthropogenic changes in this time period is applied. This results in binary change maps, consisting of all changes above or below a defined threshold. Figure 10, results represent not only land use changes driven by wind power development, but also some changes due to agricultural crop rotation or varying crop growth.

During the assessment we found Sentinel-2 band B3 (green) to be most sensitive to be used for the change detection analysis. Figure 11 shows a plot where the sum of the change values of the 3 horizontal pixels is plotted against the 3 vertical pixels, where the red dots represent all turbine locations of a region and the blue one turbines developed between 2015 and 2023. The plot clearly shows that newly erected turbines show both sums to be in a negative range, while the total population tend to show values around zero and in the positive range. Although a sharp separation is not possible, but very good results are produced.

Figure 9. Change map of a wind park in an agricultural area, grey indicating zero change, red/violet positive values, green / blue negative values.

Figure 10. Binary Change Map of the agricultural example

Figure 11. Channel 2 – change sum: vertical versus horizontal, red depicting all turbines in the analysis, blue showing the ones built between 2015 and 2023

3.1 Statistical Analysis

3.1.1 Single turbine analysis

Figure 12. Single Turbine Analysis using a 150m buffer

Figure 12 shows an exemplary single turbine analysis using a 150 buffer around each turbine. Within each buffer the index values for the change analysis are calculated. The example shows that changes do not

necessarily limit the foundation area around the base of the turbine, but also parts of the newly build or extended roads and paths contribute to the values of this analysis. The changes in percent within each of the buffer zones, approximately 707 pixels of the binary change map (70684 m²), range from 28 to 73, which translates to 2800m² to 7300m² and 3.96% to 10.33% respectively. For the IQ values in this case range from 0.06 to 0.25, the highest value representing the land use change compactness around the 4th turbine from the right, while for the SI the same area shows the lowest value with 2, with other areas ranging up to values of 4.2. While the FD shows only slight differences with values ranging from 1.45 to 1.65, showing that the complexity in terms of fractality is not suitable as an indicator in this analysis.

3.1.2 Cluster analysis

Figure 13. Cluster Analysis of newly built (2015–2023) turbines east of Vienna

Figure 13 shows the cluster analysis of new built turbines from 2015 to 2023 on the plains east of Vienna, where each colour represents wind turbines belonging to the same wind park. With this information the average distance between turbines of each cluster was calculated, buffers applied and convex and concave park areas created. An example for a wind park area created with the convex hull algorithm is displayed in Figure 14, showing the same area as the one above in the single turbine analysis example and the

same index values as the ones for the single turbine analysis are embedded within the dataset for each wind park area.

Figure 14. Convex Hull example around a single wind park area

4. OUTLOOK

Currently the data is available for a first set of countries:

- Austria
- Denmark
- Italy
- Norway
- Portugal

These exemplary countries were chosen to be processed first as they represent differing geographical, climatic and structural regions, but also all countries with pilot regions are covered. This basis now allows for a convenient and fast analysis of more countries until month 18.

Furthermore, the showcase of the statistical analysis shows that we are able to deliver valid indicators for our project partners, the stakeholders, users of the interactive map and interactive workshops in the pilot regions. The statistical values are currently examined and refined within our group and will be used for further adaptations during the first half of 2024.

For the offshore analysis we will skip the Sentinel-2 change map processing, as the locations of turbines are known. Instead, we will immediately perform statistical calculations based on literature values, especially regarding the effects on the environment.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Within the project, the generated data in T 1.2 is and will be used in consecutive tasks, as well as in the interactive web map (Web-GIS) and potentially also during the workshops in the pilot regions. The data is currently already available and will be uploaded to the YODA data exchange platform for our partners to use and also to provide room for discussion on potential changes.

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ANNEX

Figure 15 shows an example set of tiles for Italy downloaded based on turbine location information from OSM.

Figure 15. Sentinel-2 tiles with at least one wind turbine in Italy

Figure 16 and Figure 17 show an example of before and after for a mountainous region. In both examples we can see that not only the area directly around the turbine basis is affected, but also (gravel) roads are built or broadened.

Figure 16. Sentinel-2 detail of a wind park in a mountainous region before construction

Figure 17. Sentinel-2 detail of a wind park in a mountainous region after construction

Figure 18 shows a change image of the wind park in a forested mountain region.

Figure 18. Change map of a wind park in a forested mountain region, grey indicating zero change, red/violet positive values, green / blue negative values.

Figure 19. Binary change map of the mountainous area

Figure 20 and Figure 21 display examples of offshore turbines and show that a detection on water surfaces can be done using the same algorithms as for on-shore detection.

Figure 20. Change Map Offshore Turbines, grey indicating no change

Figure 21. Binary Change Map Offshore Turbines